

208	Pria	Sosial	8	Twitter (X);TikTok;Instagram;	WhatsApp;Telegram;	Tokopedia;Bukalapak;Shopee;	Ruang Guru;E-Learning Kampus;Sistem Akademik Kampus;	Sangat	5	5	4	4	5	3	4	5	5	4	4	4	5	3	5	5	4	3	5	4	4	5	5	4	
209	Pria	Sosial	4	Twitter (X);TikTok;Instagram;Linkin;	WhatsApp;Line;	Shopee;Bibli;Lazada;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;Google Classroom;Duolingo;Canva;	Sangat	5	4	4	5	3	4	5	3	5	5	4	4	4	3	5	4	4	5	5	4	5	4	5	5	4
210	Wanita	Non-Sosial	4	Twitter (X);TikTok;Instagram;	WhatsApp;Telegram;Line;	Shopee;Zalora;Lazada;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;E-Learning Kampus;Canva;Duolingo;	Sangat	5	4	4	5	4	5	3	4	5	5	4	4	4	5	5	4	4	5	4	4	2	4	3	4	1
211	Wanita	Sosial	6	Twitter (X);TikTok;Instagram;Linkin;	WhatsApp;Line;Skype;	Shopee;Bibli;Bukalapak;Lazada;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;Duolingo;Kahoot;Ruang Guru;	Sangat	5	4	4	5	3	5	5	4	4	4	5	5	5	4	4	3	4	4	2	5	4	2	5	3	2
212	Wanita	Non-Sosial	6	Twitter (X);TikTok;Instagram;	WhatsApp;Telegram;Line;	Tokopedia;Bibli;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;Ruang Guru;Duolingo;	Sangat	5	5	4	5	3	5	4	4	3	5	4	4	4	5	4	4	5	5	5	4	5	5	4	5	5
213	Wanita	Sosial	8	Twitter (X);Facebook;Linkin;Instagram;TikTok;	WhatsApp;Telegram;Line;	Shopee;Bibli;Zalora;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;Kahoot;Duolingo;E-Learning Kampus;	Sangat	5	5	4	5	5	4	3	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	2	4	5	4
214	Wanita	Non-Sosial	4	Facebook;TikTok;Instagram;	WhatsApp;Telegram;Line;	Shopee;Lazada;Bibli;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;E-Learning Kampus;Canva;Google Classroom;	Sangat	5	4	5	5	4	4	3	5	4	4	5	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	4
215	Wanita	Sosial	8	Twitter (X);TikTok;Instagram;Linkin;	WhatsApp;Telegram;Line;Skype;	Shopee;Bukalapak;Lazada;Zalora;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;E-Learning Kampus;Google Classroom;Canva;Duolingo;	Sangat	5	4	4	5	5	4	3	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	3	4	5	4	5	2
216	Wanita	Sosial	4	TikTok;	WhatsApp;	Shopee;	Duolingo;Google Classroom;Ruang Guru;E-Learning Kampus;Sistem Akademik Kampus;Canva;	Sangat	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	4	5	4	4	5	4	5
217	Pria	Non-Sosial	4	Facebook;Instagram;Linkin;	Telegram;WhatsApp;	Shopee;	Google Classroom;Sistem Akademik Kampus;E-Learning Kampus;Canva;	Sangat	5	5	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	5	4	4	3	4	3	4	4	5	3	4	4	5	5	
218	Pria	Sosial	5	Instagram;	Shopee;	Shopee;	E-Learning Kampus;Sistem Akademik Kampus;Google Classroom;	Setuju	4	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	
219	Wanita	Non-Sosial	4	Twitter (X);Instagram;TikTok;	WhatsApp;Telegram;	Shopee;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;E-Learning Kampus;Google Classroom;Canva;	Setuju	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	4	5	3	5	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	
220	Pria	Non-Sosial	3	TikTok;Instagram;Linkin;	WhatsApp;Telegram;	Shopee;TikTokShop;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;E-Learning Kampus;Google Classroom;	Sangat	5	5	4	5	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	3	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	
221	Wanita	Sosial	3	Instagram;	Telegram;WhatsApp;	Shopee;	E-Learning Kampus;Sistem Akademik Kampus;	Sangat	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	5	
222	Wanita	Sosial	2	Instagram;TikTok;	Telegram;WhatsApp;	Shopee;	E-Learning Kampus;Sistem Akademik Kampus;Google Classroom;Canva;	Sangat	5	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	5	5	5	4	5	4	5	4	4	3	3	3	3	3	
223	Pria	Non-Sosial	4	Facebook;	WhatsApp;	Shopee;	Canva;	Sangat	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	
224	Wanita	Sosial	6	Facebook;	WeChat;	Tokopedia;	Ruang Guru;	Sangat	5	4	3	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	5	3	4	4	4	5	5	
225	Pria	Sosial	6	Instagram;	Telegram;	Bukalapak;	Ruang Guru;	Setuju	4	5	4	3	4	5	4	5	4	3	4	4	5	5	4	4	3	5	5	4	3	4	4	4	
226	Wanita	Sosial	7	Instagram;	Telegram;	Bukalapak;	Duolingo;	Setuju	4	5	4	3	4	4	3	5	4	3	4	4	5	4	5	4	4	3	5	4	4	3	5	5	
227	Wanita	Sosial	6	TikTok;	Telegram;	Tokopedia;	Duolingo;	Setuju	4	3	4	5	4	3	5	4	3	4	5	4	5	4	4	3	4	5	4	5	4	3	4	4	
228	Pria	Sosial	6	TikTok;	WeChat;	Bibli;	E-Learning Kampus;	Setuju	4	5	4	3	4	5	5	5	4	3	4	4	4	5	5	4	3	4	4	4	5	4	3	4	
229	Wanita	Sosial	4	Twitter (X);	WhatsApp;	Tokopedia;	E-Learning Kampus;	Setuju	4	4	4	3	5	5	4	3	5	4	3	5	4	4	4	5	5	4	3	4	4	5	4	4	
230	Pria	Sosial	6	TikTok;	Line;	Bukalapak;	Google Classroom;	Setuju	4	3	4	5	4	3	3	5	4	3	4	5	5	4	4	4	3	5	4	5	4	3	4	4	
231	Pria	Sosial	6	Instagram;	WhatsApp;	Lazada;	Ruang Guru;	Setuju	4	5	4	4	4	5	3	4	5	4	5	4	3	3	5	4	4	4	3	4	5	4	5	4	
232	Wanita	Sosial	6	Instagram;	WhatsApp;	Bibli;	Google Classroom;	Setuju	4	5	4	3	4	5	3	4	5	3	4	5	4	3	5	4	3	4	4	3	4	5	5	5	
233	Wanita	Sosial	6	Instagram;	WhatsApp;	Tokopedia;	Ruang Guru;	Setuju	4	3	5	4	3	3	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	3	5	4	5	3	4	4	5	
234	Wanita	Sosial	6	Instagram;	WhatsApp;	Bibli;	Duolingo;	Setuju	4	3	4	5	4	4	3	4	3	5	5	4	3	3	5	4	3	3	5	4	3	4	4	4	
235	Pria	Non-Sosial	6	Instagram;	Telegram;	Tokopedia;	Google Classroom;	Setuju	4	3	5	5	5	4	3	5	4	5	4	5	3	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	5	5	
236	Pria	Sosial	7	Instagram;	Telegram;	Bukalapak;	Google Classroom;	Sangat	5	4	3	3	4	4	5	4	5	3	3	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	5	5	
237	Pria	Non-Sosial	5	Instagram;	Telegram;	Tokopedia;	Duolingo;	Setuju	4	5	3	4	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	
238	Pria	Sosial	4	Twitter (X);TikTok;Instagram;	WhatsApp;Telegram;Line;	Shopee;Bibli;Bukalapak;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;E-Learning Kampus;Duolingo;	Sangat	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	3	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	3	5	4	5	4	5	4	4	4
239	Wanita	Non-Sosial	5	Instagram;	WeChat;	Bukalapak;	Rumah Belajar;	Setuju	4	5	4	5	4	5	5	5	5	3	5	4	4	5	3	3	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	
240	Pria	Sosial	6	Facebook;TikTok;Instagram;	WhatsApp;Telegram;Skype;	Tokopedia;Lazada;Bukalapak;	E-Learning Kampus;Duolingo;Sistem Akademik Kampus;Canva;	Sangat	5	4	5	4	4	3	5	4	4	5	3	4	4	5	4	3	4	4	5	4	5	4	4	4	5
241	Wanita	Sosial	5	Instagram;	Telegram;	Bukalapak;	Duolingo;	Sangat	5	4	4	5	4	3	4	5	4	5	3	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	3	4	4	5	5	
242	Pria	Sosial	5	Instagram;	WhatsApp;	Bukalapak;Shopee;	E-Learning Kampus;	Setuju	4	5	4	4	4	4	5	4	3	5	4	4	5	3	3	4	5	4	4	3	3	3	5	5	
243	Pria	Non-Sosial	5	Instagram;	Line;	Shopee;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;	Sangat	5	4	5	4	4	4	5	4	5	4	4	5	3	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	5	5	
244	Pria	Sosial	6	Linkin;Instagram;	Line;	Lazada;	Kahoot;	Setuju	4	5	4	5	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	
245	Wanita	Sosial	4	Linkin;	WeChat;	Shopee;	Ruang Guru;	Setuju	4	4	4	3	5	4	4	3	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	3	3	4	4	5	5	5	
246	Pria	Non-Sosial	2	Twitter (X);Facebook;Instagram;Linkin;	WhatsApp;Telegram;Line;Skype;	Tokopedia;	Google Classroom;Kahoot;Canva;	Sangat	5	5	4	4	4	5	3	4	4	4	5	4	5	2	5	4	3	2	3	2	3	3	2	3	
247	Wanita	Sosial	4	Twitter (X);TikTok;Instagram;	WhatsApp;Telegram;Line;	Tokopedia;Bukalapak;Lazada;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;E-Learning Kampus;Ruang Guru;Duolingo;Canva;	Sangat	5	5	4	4	5	4	3	4	4	5	4	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	4	3	5	4	4	4	1
248	Wanita	Non-Sosial	6	Twitter (X);Facebook;Instagram;TikTok;	WhatsApp;Telegram;Line;	Shopee;Lazada;Bibli;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;E-Learning Kampus;Google Classroom;Duolingo;	Sangat	5	4	4	5	3	5	4	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	2	4	4	4	1	1
249	Pria	Sosial	5	Linkin;	Telegram;	Tokopedia;	Ruang Guru;	Setuju	4	5	4	5	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	5	5	4	5	5	4	5	4	5	4	4	
250	Wanita	Sosial	4	Facebook;Instagram;	WhatsApp;Skype;Line;Telegram;	Zalora;Lazada;Shopee;Tokopedia;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;E-Learning Kampus;Kahoot;Duolingo;	Sangat	5	4	4	5	4	3	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	3	4	5	4	4
251	Pria	Sosial	5	Instagram;	Telegram;	Bukalapak;	Ruang Guru;	Setuju	4	5	4	5	4	3	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	3	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	4	5
252	Wanita	Non-Sosial	4	TikTok;Instagram;	Telegram;WhatsApp;	Zalora;Shopee;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;E-Learning Kampus;Duolingo;Canva;	Sangat	5	4	4	5	4	4	3	5	4	4	4	5	3	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	4
253	Pria	Non-Sosial	4	Instagram;	Bukalapak;	Bukalapak;	E-Learning Kampus;	Setuju	4	4	4	5	4	5	4	3	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	4	
254	Wanita	Sosial	4	Twitter (X);Instagram;TikTok;	Telegram;WhatsApp;Line;	Shopee;Zalora;Bibli;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;E-Learning Kampus;Google Classroom;Duolingo;	Sangat	5	4	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	5	5	5
255	Wanita	Sosial	6	Twitter (X);TikTok;Instagram;	Telegram;WhatsApp;Line;	Shopee;Bibli;Bukalapak;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;E-Learning Kampus;Google Classroom;Canva;	Sangat	5	4	4	5	4	4	3	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	3	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4
256	Wanita	Sosial	4	Twitter (X);Instagram;Linkin;	WhatsApp;Telegram;Line;	Shopee;Bukalapak;Zalora;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;E-Learning Kampus;Google Classroom;Canva;Rumah Belajar;	Sangat	5	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	3	5	4	4	1	4	4	4	1	4	4	2
257	Pria	Sosial	6	TikTok;Instagram;Linkin;Twitter (X);	WhatsApp;Telegram;	Shopee;Tokopedia;Bukalapak;Lazada;	Sistem Akademik Kampus;E-Learning Kampus;Ruang Guru;Rumah Belajar;Duolingo;Kahoot;	Sangat	5	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	3	4	5	3	4	2	4	3	4	1	1	1
258	Wanita	Non-Sosial	5	Instagram;	Telegram;	Bibli;	Google Classroom;	Setuju	4	5	4	5	5	3	5	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	5	5	5	4	5	4	4	5	5	5	
259	Pria	Sosial	5	Instagram;	Telegram;	Bukalapak;	Ruang Guru;	Setuju	4	3	5	4	4	4	4	5	4	3	5	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	5	5	
260	Pria	Sosial	5	TikTok;	Line;	Bibli;	E-Learning Kampus;	Setuju	4	5	4	4	4	5	4	3	3	4	4	5	4	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	
261	Wanita	Sosial	5	Facebook;	WeChat;	Bibli;	Google Classroom;	Setuju	4	4	5	4	5	4	4	3	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	4	4	3	4
262	Pria	Non-Sosial	5	Instagram;	Skype;	Lazada;	Kahoot;	Sangat	5	5																							